

POST-LAUNCH ASSESSMENT OF THE METOP-A AMSU-A PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

After successful launch of the Advanced Microwave Sounding Unit-A (AMSU-A) onboard the Meteorological Operations Platform A (METOP-A), a systematic On-orbit Verification (OV) with on-orbit AMSU-A data was performed. Some of the OV results are reported here. Scan-by-scan examination of the radiometric calibration counts is employed to confirm normal functioning of the instrument and to detect any anomalous events, such as lunar contamination (LC) in space counts, which are detected and corrected using an algorithm for LC correction in AMSU-A data. This algorithm provides a practical approach for scan-by-scan LC correction in AMSU-A data and improves the accuracy of operational calibration of AMSU-A data. Long-term trends of the space and warm calibration counts, channel gains, housekeeping sensors, and NEAT are monitored. Monthly mean angular distributions of ocean brightness temperatures (T_B) from METOP-A and NOAA-18 over the tropical ocean region of 20°S-20°N are obtained and modeled to demonstrate that the ocean can be used as a cold reference calibration target. The establishment of a natural Earth calibration target is important for calibration of microwave radiometers. The measured ocean T_B values from the four satellites provide eight measurements across the diurnal time for studying the diurnal variation of ocean brightness temperatures which show a pattern of daytime cooling and nighttime warming.

Index Terms—Microwave Remote Sensing, AMSU-A Post-launch Calibration, Lunar Contamination Correction

1. INTRODUCTION

The Advanced Microwave Sounding Unit-A (AMSU-A) on the Meteorological Operations Platform A (METOP-A), which was launched in October 2006, was provided by NOAA. It is one of a new generation of total-power microwave radiometers which have been flown on the NOAA-15 to NOAA-18 Satellites since May 13, 1998. METOP-A was launched with initial local equator crossing time (LECT) at 9:30 a.m. for descending pass and 9:30 p.m. ascending pass. Since launch, NOAA has processed

Fig. 1. METOP-A AMSU-A NEAT values calculated with on-orbit data and compared to those from pre-launch and specifications.

the METOP data in the same way as for the data from NOAA satellites. A systematic post-launch OV of the instrumental performances was conducted with on-orbit data. NOAA and the European Organization for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT) have independently performed and compared their findings in the initial OV of the instrument performances. Some of the OV results obtained at NOAA are presented here. The temperature sensitivity (NEAT), long-term trends of the housekeeping sensors and radiometric counts from the cold space and warm targets are continuously monitored. Scan-by-scan detection and correction of LC in cold space counts is investigated. The effect of LC on the scene brightness temperatures is demonstrated. It is found that the scene antenna temperatures calculated with and without correction of LC can differ by 0.2-1.5 K depending on channels [1]. Monthly mean angular distributions of ocean brightness temperatures from METOP-A, NOAA-18, -16, and -15 over the tropical ocean region of 20°S-20°N are obtained and modeled to demonstrate that the ocean can be used as a cold reference calibration target. The eight measurements of ocean T_B values from the four satellites across the diurnal time provide an opportunity for studying the diurnal variation of ocean brightness temperatures which show a pattern of daytime cooling and nighttime warming [2]. The results of METOP OV are presented in Section 2. Detection and correction of LC is described in Section 3. The observation of ocean T_B and its diurnal variation are given in Section 4.

Fig. 2. Long-term trend of NEAT in 2007.

Fig. 3. Long-term trend of daily mean space counts in 2007. The two data breaks at days 110 and 270 are due to METOP-A anomalies which caused AMU-A to shut down.

Fig. 4. Orbital cycles and diurnal variation of RF Shelf temperatures over January 1, 2007.

2. ON-ORBIT VERIFICATION OF METOP-A DATA

The METOP-A AMSU-A NEAT values calculated from pre-launch and on-orbit data are shown in Fig. 1. The NEAT is defined as the minimum change in a scene radiometric temperature that can be detected. In practice, it is calculated as the standard deviation of radiometric outputs of an antenna system that looks at a scene target at a constant temperature (normally 300K). Each of the on-orbit NEAT values was calculated from the blackbody radiometric temperatures over one orbit (~800 scans) during which the blackbody temperature variation was of order of 0.1 K. All of the on-orbit NEAT values in Fig. 1 meet the AMSU-A specifications. The long-term trends of NEAT in 2007 are shown in Fig. 2 which shows that the NEAT values are stable most of the time, but do have small fluctuations at certain channels (for example channels 1 and 2). Fig. 3 shows the long-term trends of daily means of the radiometric space calibration counts versus Julian day in 2007. The variations in these counts are due to instrument temperature (which is defined as the RF-Shelf temperature) variation. Normally, the counts increase when the instrument temperature decreases and vice versa. Fig. 4 shows the orbital cycles and diurnal trends of the three RF Shelf temperatures over January 1, 2007.

Fig. 5. METOP-A AMSU-A lunar contamination as shown by the sharp spikes occurred on December 27, 2007. After correction of the LC, the remaining space counts (without LC) are shown by the red curves under the spikes.

3. CORRECTION OF LUNAR CONTAMINATION

When the moon appears in the space view, the space counts are contaminated since the lunar surface temperature is much higher than the deep space cosmic background radiation temperature of 2.73 K. Following a recent investigation [1], the LC in space counts, ΔC_c , can be expressed in terms of the channel gain and the increased space brightness temperature ΔT_c due to the lunar surface temperature by the formula,

$$\Delta C_c = \left[\frac{C_w - C_c}{T_w - (T_c + \Delta T_c)} \right] \Delta T_c \quad (1)$$

where the increased space temperature ΔT_c is related to the effective lunar surface temperature T_{moon} by [1],

$$\Delta T_c = \exp \left[-\frac{(\alpha - \alpha_0)^2}{2\alpha_s^2} \right] \exp \left[-\frac{(\delta - \delta_0)^2}{2\delta_s^2} \right] \beta T_{moon} r \quad (2)$$

and

$$T_{moon} = 95.21 + 10463(1 - \cos\theta) + 11.62(1 + \cos 2\theta) \quad (3)$$

where:

- θ separation angle between the moon and sun
- C_w blackbody count
- C_c observed space counts, including LC
- T_w blackbody temperature

Fig. 6. Detection of LC in METOP-A AMSU-A space counts at channel 6

- T_c deep space cosmic background temperature
- α lunar azimuth angle
- α_0 field of view center of lunar azimuth angle
- α_s lunar azimuth size factor
- δ lunar elevation angle
- δ_0 field of view center of lunar elevation angle
- δ_s lunar elevation size factor
- β area ratio of lunar disk to FOV convolved with the antenna patterns powers
- r distance ratio = $(60.3 \times 6378/d)^2$, where d is the distance (in km) between the satellite and moon.

Fig. 5 shows a set of samples of the AMSU-A LC (sharp spikes) occurred on December 27, 2007. Eq. (1) is used to make LC correction, after which, the remaining space counts are shown by the red curves under the spikes. More detailed description can be found elsewhere [1]. LC is significant only when the separation angle μ between the moon and the cold space viewing direction is less than 4° , beyond which LC is negligible as the AMSU-A antenna power drops 40 dB below its peak. This provides a practical approach for scan-by-scan LC correction in AMSU-A data to improve the accuracy of the operational calibration of NOAA Level 1B data. The correlation between the μ angle and the lunar contamination is demonstrated in Fig. 6. It shows the calculated μ angles (top panel) and the space counts (middle panel). The horizontal line is the μ angle of 4° . LC reaches maximum at $\mu=0^\circ$. The LC effect on scene temperatures is shown in Fig. 6 (lower part) with ΔT_s denoting the difference of scene temperatures with and without LC correction.

Fig. 7. METOP-A AMSU-A monthly mean brightness temperatures over ocean. Data from ascending pass (9:30 p.m.) are shown as ++ and those from descending pass (9:30 a.m.) by xx. Solid curves are model simulations [2].

Fig. 8. Same as Fig.7, except data are from NOAA-18 with ascending pass near 1:42 p.m. and descending pass near 1.42 a.m.

Fig. 9. Diurnal variation of ocean brightness temperatures measured with AMSU-As on METOP-A, NOAA-15, -16, and -18. Note the pattern of nighttime warming and daytime cooling.

4. BRIGHTNESS TEMPERATURES OVER OCEAN

Angular distributions of observed T_B from the METOP-A (Fig. 7), NOAA-18 (Fig. 8) -16, and -15 AMSU-As over the ocean region of 20°S-20°N are obtained and compared. The AMSU-A data from the four satellites provide eight T_B measurements across diurnal time and are used for investigation of the diurnal variation of the T_B over ocean (Fig. 9). Surprisingly, it shows a trend of daytime cooling and nighttime warming even though the sea surface temperatures at daytime are warmer than those of nighttime. Figs. 7 and 8 show the monthly mean T_B data over ocean in (a) January and (b) April 2007. Pluses are the data from ascending pass and crosses are those of descending passes. Solid curves are simulations [2]. Note that the T_B values in daytime are smaller than those of nighttime. More detailed discussion is given elsewhere [2].

5. REFERENCES

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